

ISic3190

I.Sicily inscription 3190

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Vigna Cassia

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329584

1. Πιστάρα κὲ Νίκη κὲ Συρακόσις κὲ Πραϋλὶς κὲ
2. Μο-
3. νέ-
4. ρις ²⁶Muneri²⁶
5. ἀπὸ Νήσου.
6. ²in circulo:² □
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645520

PHI 329584

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3190. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388306>